

Educational Planning: Paradigm for Effective Administration and Management of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

BY

AYENI, Catherine Folake Ph.D.

Adeyemi Federak University of Education,

Department of Educational Mangement, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

ayenicf@gmail.com

&

OLAOLU, Bilikisu Oluwakemi

Adeyemi Federak University of Education,

Department of Educational Management, Ondo, Ondo State, Nigeria.

kennygold1012@gmail.com

Abstract

The study was carried out on educational planning as paradigm for effective administration and management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Descriptive survey research design was used. The population of the study comprised administrative and management personnel at tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The sample size of the study was Three hundred (300) respondents selected through a simple random sampling technique. Fifty (50) respondents were selected from each of the first established university in each of the six geo-political regions in Nigeria (North-Central, North-East, North-West, South-East, South-South and South-West). Two research questions were raised to guide the conduct of the study. A self-structured research instrument titled, "Questionnaire on Educational Planning as Paradigm for Effective Administration and Management of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria". It was fashioned on four likert rating scale; Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD) and rated on 4; 3; 2; and 1, respectively. The research instrument were validated by two experts in Test and Measurement, while its reliability was done through test retest method at two weeks interval and 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained. Data generated were analyzed through descriptive statistics simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}). Based on the results, conclusion were made that educational planning could facilitate a judicious use of financial resources and positioning of personnel for optimal productivity. Recommendations were made based on the result that certificate in educational planning should be made compulsory for personnel in

administrative unit of tertiary institution in Nigeria. Also, they should be attending in-service training on a continual basis on educational planning.

Keyword: Educational Planning, Paradigm, Administration, Management, Tertiary Institution

Background to the Study

Globally or all over the world, education has been identified and singled out to be a major key to development of the nations. Sarumi (2001), strongly asserted that there is no nation that can tower beyond her level of educational attainment. Erinsakin (2018), noted that education is a “sine-qua-non” to a sustainable development of nations and individuals.

Oyekan (2004), maintained that education is very critical to human development in a holistic context. Education is empowerment to fish for justice, break the yoke of poverty, stands for one’s right(s), develop critical thinking and minds. Education enable one’s to solve his or her challenges and be contributing meaningfully to his or her environment in terms of development. Therefore, government efforts at all levels specifically, in developing nations, Nigeria inclusively in the 21st century focusing on ensuring quality and inclusive education is provided to her citizenry.

Specifically, in Nigeria, several policies, force, conferences, seminars, workshops have been continuous activities towards ensuring and guaranteeing quality education for the Nigeria. In the same vein, the Federal Government of Nigeria (FGN) have been synergizing effort and collaborating educational activities with international organizations like’ United Nations Educational and Scientific Organization (UNESCO), World Bank (WB) and host of others towards revamping the present state or level of educational development in the country.

Observably, the level of development and attainment in Nigeria is still a major concern and worry to stakeholders in educational sector in the country. Oyekan (2004), attributes the gory state to several factors poor schools' administration and management is one.

In a simple term, school administration is the management of all schools operation which entails planning, organizing, assembling, resources, supervising, controlling, discipline and so on. Also, it is working with and through people within the school community to get things done effectively (Kochhar, 2011). Educational management is the administration of the educational system in which a group combined human and material resources to supervise, plan strategies and implement structures to execute an educational system. Administration and management of both the human and non-human resources are vital factors that could result into achieving schools' vision and mission statements. However, educational planning has been identified as a catalyst or fundamental towards achieving effective school administration and management. Akpan (2011) conceptualized planning as the process of examining the future and drawing up on mapping out a course of action for achieving specified goals and objectives. It is a process of making rational and technical choice. Planning is a systematic, conscious and deliberate process of deciding ahead of time, the future course of action that a person wishes to pursue in order to achieve or reach set goals. This definition suggests that planning is part and parcel of every man endeavor politically, socially, economically and academically.

UNESCO (2003), explained planning as a process that makes it possible to work out a systematic outline of activities to be undertaken in order to meet the developmental objectives of a country within that country's aspirations and possibilities. Erinsakin (2020) therefore defined

educational planning to involve a systematic and scientific set of decisions for future action with the aim of achieving set out educational goals and objectives through effective use of scarce resources.

Beeby cited in Okwori (2011) stated that educational planning is the exercise foresights in determining the policy, priorities and cost of educational system having due regards for economic and political realities for the system potentials, for growth and for the needs of the country and of the pupils served by the system. The future development of a nation is the focus of educational planning. It involves studying the future educational needs of country and putting in place relevant policies and priorities, actions and programmes that will enhance achievement of set out educational goals.

Educational planning does not just happen by chance. It is an organized social practice involving studying the present and using available information concerning the educational challenges of a country to pan for future educational needs and development.

As observed, numerous studies both positional and empirical have been carried out on several issues on schools administration and management. The researcher of the present study, specifically, study has not been done empirically on educational planning and it impact or influence on effective school administration and management, specifically on tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It was this gap that motivated the researcher to carry out the study.

Statement of the Problem

The focus on educational sector specifically in developing nation, Nigeria, inclusively is necessitated by its values to individuals and nations, thus, informing strategies to improve the

sector. In this context, educational planning is one of the key areas, specifically, how it enhance effective school administration and management of tertiary institutions in Nigeria. It was against this background the study was carried out.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of the study research was on planning as paradigm for effective tertiary institutions administration and management in Nigeria while, the specific objectives were to;

- i. ascertain the impact of educational planning on managing financial resources judiciously in tertiary institutions in Nigeria; and
- ii. determine the influence of educational planning on human resources optimal productivity in tertiary institutions in Nigeria.

Research Questions

Two research questions were raised to guide the study.

1. Can educational planning facilitate effective managing of financial resources, judiciously in tertiary institutions in Nigeria?
2. Can human resources optimal productivity be achieved through effective educational planning in tertiary institutions in Nigeria?

Conceptual Framework

1. Planning

The term planning is a subject of pluralism in terms of definition and explanation Undie, Ekere and Adah (2011), defined planning as identification of goals and objectives of

organization and working out ways and means of achieving them. Planning is a conscious, systematic and deliberate process of action that a person wishes to pursue in any field of human endeavor.

Erinsakin (2018), planning is usually done with the intension of achieving the defined goals and objectives in any organization. Planning is an inherent attribute of man. Everyday we are planning so as not to fail.

2. Educational Planning

Educational planning is targeted mainly to achieve the set goals on education. Planning provides the direction towards achieving some specific goals on education. Akpan (2000) defined it as an intelligent preparation and actions to guide future challenges in the course of achieving set goals in educational sector. It is a process of making rational and technical choice. It is a process of identifying and classifying educational needs of a nation and the direction education should take and the strategies for implementing decisions concerning educational development. Educational planning should reflect the state of development of a nation including the needs and readiness to execute the planned objectives.

The following are the characteristics of educational planning;

- i. It should be dynamic
- ii. It should be comprehensive
- iii. Educational planning should be integrates
- iv. It should be iterative
- v. It should be goal oriented (Obi, 2003).

In a nutshell, the central or cardinal goal of educational planning is to achieve educational goals and objectives. Others are educational planning gives direction, enhances continuity, save time and resources wastage, maintain standard, and so on.

Fig. 1: Educational Planning Mechanism

Sources: Adapted from Ololufe N.P (2013)

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used for the study. The study population comprised, administrative and management personnel at tertiary institutions in Nigeria. The sample size of the study was Three hundred (300), selected through a simple random sampling technique. Fifty (50) respondents were selected from the first established university from each of the Geo-Political zones in Nigeria: North-Central, North-East, North-West, South-East, South-South and South-West.

North-Central: University of Jos (1975)

North-East: University of Maiduguri, (1975)

North-West: Ahmadu Bello University (1962)

South-East: University of Nigeria, Nsukka (1955)

South-South: University of Port-Harcourt (1975)

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South-West: University of Ibadan (1948)

Two research questions were raised for the study. A self-developed research instrument titled, “Questionnaire on Educational Planning : Paradigm towards Effective Administration and Management of Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria”. It was fashioned on four likert rating scale; Strongly Agreed (SA), Agreed (A), Disagreed (D) and Strongly Disagreed (SD), rated on 4; 3; 2 and 1, respectively.

The research instrument were validated by two experts in Test and Measurement while it reliability was done through test-retest method at two weeks interval and 0.68 coefficient reliability was obtained using descriptive statistics (simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x})).

Presentation of Findings and Discussion of Results

Presentation of Findings

Research Question One: Can educational planning facilitate effective managing of Financial Resources judiciously in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria?

Table 1: Showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}) on can Educational Planning Facilitate Effective Managing of Financial Resources Judiciously in Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

		N = 300,				C = 2.5			
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision	
1	Educational planning will aid even distribution of financial resources to tertiary institution in Nigeria	253 84.33	23 7.66	15 5	9 3	300	3.73	Accepted	
2	Even distribution of financial resources to tertiary institutions may not be achieved through educational planning	19 6.33	1 0.33	33 11	247 82.33	300	1.30	Rejected	
3	Through educational planning	276	13	9	2	300	3.87	Accepted	

	scarce financial resources can be effectively used in tertiary institutions in Nigeria	92	4.33	3	0.66			
4	Educational planning will not result into scarce financial resources utilization in tertiary institutions in Nigeria	5 1.66	15 5	34 11.33	246 82	300	1.26	Rejected
5	Educational planning will reduce waste of limited financial resources	266 88.66	19 6.33	9 3	6 2	300	3.81	Accepted
6	Educational planning will not reduce wastage of limited financial resources	27 9	13 4.33	19 6.33	241 80.33	300	1.42	Rejected
7	Financial budgeting at tertiary institution could be enhanced through educational planning	271 92.33	12 4	8 2.66	3 1	300	3.87	Accepted
8	Educational planning will not enhance financial budgeting at tertiary institutions in Nigeria	9 3	9 3	17 5.66	265 88.33	300	1.20	Rejected
	TOTAL WEIGHT	1,132 47.16	105 4.37	144 6	1,019 42.45		2.55	Accepted

Keys:

N = Total Number of respondents

\bar{x} = Mean

C = Cut off point

SA = Strongly Agreed

A = Agreed

D = Disagreed

SD = Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 1 above presents findings on research question one as follows: On item (1), the responses obtained were 253 (84.33), 23 (7.66), 15 (5) and 9 (3) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (2), the following responses were got; 19 (6.33), 1 (0.33), 33 (11) and 247 (82.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (3), 276 (92), 13 (4.33), 9 (3) and 2 (0.66) for strongly agreed, agreed,

disagreed and strongly disagreed were obtained. On item (4) also, responses got showed 5 (1.66), 15 (5), 34 (11.33) and 246 (82) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

On item (5), the following responses were got; 266 (88.66), 19 (6.33), 9(3), 6 (2) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (6), responses obtained indicated, 27 (9), 13 (4.33), 19 (6.33) and 241 (80.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, also. On item (7), the following responses were also obtained, 277 (92.33), 12 (4), 8 (2.66) and 3 (1) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Finally, the result obtained on item (8) revealed, 9 (3), 9 (3), 17 (5.66) and 265 (88.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, also.

Generally speaking, the result indicated that educational planning could facilitate effective managing of financial resources judiciously in tertiary institutions in Nigeria. Since, the average mean rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.5$) was lesser than the mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.55$).

Research Question Two: Can Human Resources Optimal Productivity be Achieved through Effective Educational Planning at Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria?

Table 2: Showing simple percentages, frequency counts and mean (\bar{x}) on can Human Resources Optimal Productivity be Achieved through Effective Educational Planning at Tertiary Institutions in Nigeria

		N = 300,		C = 2.5				
S/N	ITEMS	SA %	A %	D %	SD %	N	Mean (\bar{x})	Decision
9	Educational planning will result into assigning duties to schools personnel appropriately	251 83.66	33 11	14 4.66	2 0.66	300	3.77	Accepted
10	Assigning duties to personnel appropriately cannot be	9 3	1 0.33	55 18.33	235 78.33	300	1.28	Rejected

	facilitated through educational planning							
11	Employment of qualified personnel can be done through Educational Planning	261 87	33 11	2 0.66	4 1.33	300	3.83	Accepted
12	Educational planning may not guarantee employment of qualified personnel	6 2	19 6.33	31 10.33	244 81.33	300	1.29	Rejected
13	Educational planning will lead to formulating of policies that will motivate personnel to work well	14 4.66	2 0.66	13 4.33	271 90.33	300	1.19	Rejected
14	Educational planning has nothing to do with personnel motivation towards better job performance	231 77	33 11	18 6	18 6	300	3.59	Accepted
15	Educational planning will enable personnel to focus on their duties	2 0.66	12 4	23 7.66	262 87.66	300	1.17	Rejected
16	Personnel can still focus on their duties through educational planning	267 89	13 4.33	8 2.66	12 4	300	3.78	Accepted
	TOTAL WEIGHT	1,041 43.37	146 6.08	164 6.83	1,049 43.70		2.5	Accepted

Keys:

N = Total Number of respondents

\bar{x} = Mean

C = Cut off point

SA = Strongly Agreed

A = Agreed

D = Disagreed

SD = Strongly Disagreed

Source: Field Survey, 2025

Table 2 above, shows the findings on research question one. On item (9), the following responses were got; 251 (83.66), 33 (11), 14 (4.66) and 2 (0.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (10), the following responses were obtained; 9 (3), 1

(0.33), 55 (18.33) and 235 (78.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (11), responses obtained indicated; 261 (87), 33 (11), 2 (0.66) and 4 (1.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed. On item (12), the following responses were obtained; 6 (2), 19 (6.33), 31 (10.33) and 244 (81.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively.

On item (13), responses got showed; 14 (4.66), 2 (0.66), 13(4.33) and 271 (90.33) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, also. On item (14), responses got showed, 231 (77), 33 (11), 18 (6) and 18 (6) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, respectively. On item (15) also, the following responses were got; 2 (0.66), 12 (4), 23 (7.66) and 263 (87.66) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed.

Finally, on item (16), the responses obtained were 267 (89), 13 (4.33), 8 (2.66) and 12 (4) for strongly agreed, agreed, disagreed and strongly disagreed, also.

The total weight of the results showed that educational planning could improve human resources productivity, optimally at tertiary institutions in Nigeria, since, the average mean of four ($\bar{x} = 2.5$) was not greater than the mean of average rating scale of four ($\bar{x} = 2.5$).

Discussion of Results

The total weight of findings indicated that educational planning could result into judicious managing of financial resources at tertiary institutions in Nigeria, effectively. The result aligns with the option of Obi (2003) that the measure financial resources or fund that is being allocated to educational institution required careful educational planning. Further, that, in

the face of economic dwindling situation with educational budgets and revenue far less than demands of services calls for strategic planning.

The result on research questions two which indicated that educational planning could improved and enhanced human resources efficiency, productivity and optimal service delivery. The result also in consonance with the view and stance of Akpan (2000) that intelligent educational planning could result into strategic positioning of personnel to work optimally towards achieving educational set goals and objectives.

Conclusion

Based on the results of the study, conclusions were made that educational planning is a vital tool to put into scarce fund or financial resources into use, judiciously. Also, that personnel in the tertiary institutions in Nigeria could be made to be productive in terms of service delivery with a careful and strategic educational planning.

Recommendations

Based on the conclusions, the following were made by the researchers;

1. Certificates in educational planning should be made a compulsory requirement for personnel in administrative unit of tertiary institutions in Nigeria.
2. Workshops and seminars on a continual basis should be organized for the managers or personnel at the management level tertiary institutions in Nigeria.
3. The managers of tertiary institutions should be sensitized on the need to avail themselves with educational planning courses and its benefits to administration and management of educational organizations

4. The stakeholders in school administration and management should be made to be aware of different techniques of achieving effective management of schools. This can be made possible through regular in-service training programme.

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